

Quantum-Safe Cryptography for UWB and IoT Networks-A survey

Salwa M Din*
Department of Advanced Studies
York University
Toronto, Ontario, CA
salkammd@my.yorku.ca

November 24, 2024

Abstract

Quantum-safe cryptography has been proposed in recent years because of the security vulnerabilities of the widely deployed cryptographic algorithms against quantum computers. The wide adoption of IoT devices and UWB technologies is expected in future years; therefore, it is crucial to protect private information against eavesdropping and quantum computer attacks. A quantum computer can break the public classical key system that relies on integer factoring and finding discrete logarithm problems, such as RSA and ECC, in polynomial time. Instead of a classical approach, these IoT devices should utilize different cryptography techniques resistant to quantum computing attacks in future work. A robust public cryptographic algorithm is necessary to ensure the security of business-oriented devices in relation to data integrity and confidentiality, as they are expected to prevail in forthcoming years.

The non-recoverable features pose a serious challenge in UWB and IoT systems as new prospective wireless communication paradigms and cryptographic methods should be investigated in the quantum computing era to address eavesdropping and data security objectives. Therefore, continuous research and investigation in cryptographic systems are required to address future challenges and propose quantum-resistant scheme-based solutions, in turn making system resiliency strong against quantum computer advancements. The cryptanalytic capabilities of quantum computers are expected to pose a serious threat to traditional public lattice cryptographic solutions subjected to integer factorization and solving univariate polynomial equations over a small field, which could defile the confidentiality and integrity of the system. Therefore, this review focuses on the exploration and investigation of the quantum computing paradigm, identifying the

*Use footnote for providing further information about author (salkam)—*not* for acknowledging funding agencies.

challenges faced by ultra-wideband technology and offering an analysis of quantum-safe cryptographic techniques in the post-quantum cryptography era.

Index Terms: UWB, Impulse Radio, WSN, Blockchain , Cyber attack, Cryptography, Compliance Management, IoT , Privacy, Security.

1 Introduction

Cryptography is an essential factor in securing data transmission in the smart world. Traditional cryptography based on RSA, ECDH, and EDSA algorithms is considered secure against classical computing attacks. However, the transition to quantum cryptography becomes essential given the advancement in the field of quantum computing. Studies have shown that a quantum computer can break all existing public-key cryptosystems, including RSA and ECC. The impact of quantum computing on location-based cryptographic methods in UWB is discussed[1]. A quantum-safe solution for secure communication, PSK, in UWB technologies is studied. The entangled photons are discussed for providing security in UWB radar-based localization. Wireless communication technology has received much attention in the last decade with the deployment of the Internet of Things (IoT) [2]. Impressive applications have been developed for different domains such as healthcare, biomedical, smart home, smart cities, e-health, and social distancing. Localization is the backbone of communication in smart technologies. Ultra-wideband (UWB) is an advanced communication technology used to develop precise localization techniques [3]. Time difference of arrival (TDOA) of UWB signals is used to develop many location-based cryptographic algorithms and architectures. Several cryptographic solutions are discussed and integrated with UWB technology to ensure secure communication. The impact of quantum computing on time delay-based location keys is discussed. The aim of this study is to highlight the importance of quantum-safe cryptography for UWB technology. In this direction, the impact of quantum computing is discussed on different location technologies, i.e., Global Positioning System, Wireless Local Area Network, and RADAR [4] . A detailed study on UWB technology and the IoT architecture is conducted to emphasize the importance of quantum-safe cryptography to secure information in UWB and IoT networks.

1.1 Background on Quantum Computing and Cryptography

The rise of quantum computing potentially threatens widely adopted cryptographic algorithms. Quantum computers have different principles and computational capabilities due to quantum mechanics. Quantum computing uses superposition, where a qubit can be both 1 and 0 at the same time [5] . Quantum entanglement creates higher information capacities. Large numbers of qubits lead to exponential growth in computational abilities, making RSA and ECC algorithms vulnerable to brute force attacks [6] .

Before the rise of quantum research, classical infrastructures with efficient computing algorithms were developed and deployed. RSA, ECC, and DH cryptographic algorithms became widely adopted for encryption mechanisms [7]. However, adversarial quantum computing has made these algorithms vulnerable to future threats. The rise of quantum computers must be resisted to protect global AI blockchain and IoT revolution, including Ultra Wide Band-IoT networks. Blockchain and IoT technology pose challenges in protecting cryptographic secret keys from side-channel attacks.

1.2 Significance of Quantum-Safe Cryptography in UWB and IoT Networks

The attack enactment and experimentation mechanisms in different computing environments, such as cloud, are easy to establish and are already well-prevalent, which makes them more vulnerable in case of an exposure of prevailing cryptographic systems to quantum cryptanalysis due to the computational prowess of quantum computing [8]. An improvement in computation time accelerated to many orders of magnitude can expose the unbounded network operations if operated across secure nodes connected to one another, and at the server against prospective eavesdroppers if accessing the shareable wireless communication link [9]. UWB networks pose various challenges from the cryptographic point of view, including side-channel security, low-cost computation ability of the nodes, rapid collection and transportation of embedded devices like wireless sensors that are deployed in the UWB network, distinct cryptography routing, and time synchronization. UWB technology is an alternative defense against such threats, bringing in phase ultrawideband by considering the distance from the tradition of multipath spread frequency systems [10][11]. However, this transition also ensures a quantum-resistant solution for UWB networks for secure communication systems at the physical layer. IoT networks are more than a set of connected devices and systems. They are an end-to-end ecosystem with extraordinary software stacks and application program interfaces. In order to ensure that legitimate devices remain bounded, an extraordinary layer of unremovable security is demanded in the provisioning, commissioning, and lifecycle management of these devices. An IoT integrated with UWB as a secure link key ensures interoperability, with backup even with power cargo, and active radio modules, faster tracking, resource consumption, and uninterrupted operation [12]. The various applications envisioned in UWB-integrated IoT encompass smart buildings, hotel registration, swimming pool checking, power plants, smart industrial oils, plastic granules, tires, integrated consumer/health monitoring devices, and health retina scanning or MRI feedback at the doctor/patient end. Moreover, the years of communication information are useless and are easily converted to a series of random numeric values that make it intricate to visualize the information set of open area trading to the quantum invaders [13][14].

2 Overview of UWB Technology

Ultra-Wideband (UWB) communication technology is ideal for low-power, high bandwidth short range communication like the Internet of Medical Things or the Internet of Things. UWB allows for low-power communication through noise-like, short, and infinitesimally low-power pulses. UWB is expected to transfer data at faster rates, making it suitable for in-house communications with short-range, low-power devices. UWB devices have the advantage of collecting low-energy at short distances without increase over transmission distance. UWB is a great solution for indoor mobile location-aware distributed sensor networks, with applications including tracking, advertising, gaming, and robot communication.

Ultra-Wideband is a digital wireless technology used for short distances and utilizes a large portion of bandwidth. UWB technology is mainly used in radar systems and location services. The transmitted signal is a low-power radiofrequency pulse. The spectrum of the UWB signal has a fractional bandwidth greater than 20% or a bandwidth of at least 500 MHz. The use of UWB in IoT and medical IoT requires the security of this technology against certain threats. UWB technology has a bright future and is being invested in by industries such as healthcare, automotive, smartphone manufacturers, and smart homes. UWB is particularly useful to establish a communication medium among IoT devices at home with high-rate data transfer. Precise synchronization of wireless carts with control systems can improve their performance and reduce costs. UWB uses a low power signal and introduces frequency diversity. To counteract narrowband interference, UWB communication systems use differentiated binary modulation. UWB also serves as an SRD policy for radar sensors.

2.1 Applications in IoT Networks

Beyond the UWB systems or applications introduced in the former section, UWB technology has further broad applicability in the IoT network, such as smart healthcare and automotive sectors. For example, in healthcare, precision surgery is an advanced operating hygienic method adopted minimally for observation and therapy to reduce the damage of risk elements. In the present scenario, most hospitals use diathermy devices to stop the blood due to any cause of bleeding apart from operation. Especially, the UWB radio frequency transmission enables the working of the pack of devices connected through the IoT [15]. This is a small part of many features that the IoT of UWB technology can offer, such as remote surgery, safety, and so on. Also, there are still a great number of applications that UWB technology has achieved for more sectors, including intelligent agriculture, intelligent health, intelligent transportation, three-dimensional positioning, real-time tracking, and so on [16].

The introduction of UWB into IoT is expected to dramatically increase real-precision positioning capability, data interaction rate, and instantaneous networking capacity by enabling precise data-free transmission time. In addition, UWB's seamless combination with IoT devices can improve the read/write efficiency, security, and stability of IoT devices, and enhance user experience [17]

. The major implementations of UWB include sensor networks for industrial control and monitoring, wireless USB, logistics management and inventories, intelligent healthcare provision, autonomous vehicle systems, building construction, education, and entertainment. UWB wireless technology thus is becoming a key and integrated part of the one-go development plan for various next-generation wireless Internet of Things technology platforms towards intelligent transport systems and creating/advancing smart cities, intelligent infrastructure, and Industry 4.0. After UWB technology becomes popular, there will be issues with the confirmation of certain standards and agreements on interface specifications. This leads to the challenge of UWB devices interoperating with different types of wireless devices [18].

3 Challenges in Securing UWB and IoT Networks

UWB and IoT have a plethora of applications and have become part of our everyday lives. The interconnection of billions of IoT devices embedded in homes, energy systems, traffic systems, and industry, along with the information systems relying on UWB, makes networks carrying them susceptible to cybersecurity attacks. In IoT systems, the level of inherent protection by obscurity and the strict constraints on energy require devices and sensors to have minimal computation, memory, and tamper resistance, making them easy targets for attackers [19]. A significant challenge for securing UWB and IoT networks lies in selecting cryptographic primitives that are secure against even the emerging quantum computing attacks, implementing them with the above resource-constrained devices, and deploying them across the globe of interconnected UWB and IoT networks [20].

Traditional cryptosystems, based on RSA, ECC, and other cryptographic primitives, are susceptible to quantum attacks. RSA relies on the difficulty of integer factorization to identify uniquely large prime numbers from their product, and ECC relies on the hardness of the elliptic curve discrete logarithm problem. Classical computers compute the product of numbers via multiplication independently of the digits in the two operands, making them perform significantly slower as the number of digits increases [21]. Because all encrypted connections are openly stored, an adversary capable of deploying expensive quantum algorithms could factor the product, identifying the two primes of RSA encryption, and solve the elliptic curve discrete logarithm problem. As a security industry, it is vital to raise awareness in the cybersecurity community about potential attacks, quantify the practicality of quantum algorithms, and enhance or replace the current protocols in the advent of fully functional quantum-resistant cryptosystems and protocols. With this motivation in mind, we focus in this work on potential quantum-safe solutions to two different application domains, namely UWB and IoT.

3.1 Vulnerabilities of Traditional Cryptography in the Quantum Era

The field of quantum computing offers computational benefits, especially in breaking cryptographic systems. This requires a shift to quantum-safe cryptographic schemes. Shor's algorithm and Grover's quantum search algorithm are widely used for cryptographic primitives. Shor's algorithm efficiently factors large integers used in RSA and breaks elliptic curve cryptography. This poses a threat to data confidentiality in networks using DSS, SSL/TLS, and cryptocurrencies. Post-quantum cryptography can also factorize large prime numbers.

Cryptographic primitives enable secure authenticity of data in wireless networks. Quantum-safe cryptographic primitives are needed to protect against quantum threats. Research is essential to develop and use secret keys for data authentication and integrity in these networks.

4 Quantum-Safe Cryptographic Solutions

In the light of known quantum algorithms, public key or asymmetric cryptographic systems are in danger. It is crucial to develop cryptographic systems and schemes that will be able to withstand the power, i.e., efficiency and computational capabilities, of large-scale quantum computers [22]. This can be achieved by adding a large space and high dimension to the search set, disassociating the use of quantum resources from the time and space complexity that a classical computer employs, or increasing the number of potential solutions in an algorithmic step to equal the volume, i.e., space, that a quantum computer uses at the end of its computational execution. This high dimension, large space, increasing the complexity, or large volume should be applied in the current complex research tasks for quantum-safe cryptographic solutions [23].

Lattice-based cryptography is the most mature. Post-quantum cryptographic solutions are promising due to the assumed complexity of typical NP-complete problems, to solve which the classical computer must work in exponential time. This is reinforced by hard learning problems, going back to the ancient Greek Euclidean Algorithm and a subset sum problem that is equivalent to either gaps in prime numbers or greatest common divisor problems [24]. Code-based cryptography is another good direction. Security requires a range of fault-secure correction codes, and it is very easy to construct. While other cryptosystems are currently being developed, these are the best cryptographic candidates for a future cryptographically secure communication era. The code multiplication cryptosystem quantum breaks. The cryptosystem mentioned used the characteristics of the problem of information theory and coding theory. The original version of the cryptosystem is difficult to break even with sublinear advancements; therefore, correct secondary versions are still challenging to crack. Draft guidelines for selecting algorithms for post-quantum cryptography are being prepared. Signatures can move faster than public-key systems, so one of the winners of the call may be a reasonable choice [25]. However, it is also

best to speed things up and see what cryptanalysis can be done by the world congress of cryptographers. In this section, we provide the mechanisms behind the various systems and their feasibility for UWB communications.

4.1 Lattice-Based Cryptography

Lattice-based crypto secures algorithms from quantum attacks. Hardness of lattice problems enables quantum-safe security. Lattice theory deals with space tiling. Key problems include Shortest Independent Vector, Learning with Error, and Ring Learning with Error. These problems ensure post-quantum security [26].

Quantum computers can break public-key cryptographic functions. Post-quantum cryptography aims to address this issue with standardization. Lattice-based schemes, like Minimum Memory and NewHope, are being considered for standardization. These schemes are efficient in high-efficiency networks, but trade-offs with security and performance must be considered. Research is focused on improving efficiency in conventional and wireless networks. Standardization can prevent the use of insecure protocols and adapt to quantum computer advancements [27]. IoT devices need to incorporate quantum-resistant solutions. Standardization is necessary for updating protocols and algorithms in response to attacks.

4.2 Code-Based Cryptography

Error correction codes, like Reed-Solomon codes, are essential for code-based cryptography. They fix errors in a message sent over a noisy channel, making it difficult for attackers to determine the original message without error correction. These codes can be used to create cryptographic primitives, where security relies on the challenge of decoding and correcting numerous errors [28]. Decoding these primitives without the private algorithm is known as the syndrome decoding problem, and its security is tied to the minimum distance of the codes. Code-based cryptography has been explored in the realms of secure multiparty computation and digital signatures.

The McEliece and Niederreiter systems show promise. Advances have improved McEliece's key size. Both systems have withstood public scrutiny. Code-based protocols have been approved in post-quantum cryptography. Code-based systems have advantages over lattice and hash-based systems. Constant performance and large key sizes are challenges. Ongoing research and collaboration are happening in code-based cryptography [29].

We welcome examples of quantum-safe communication technologies with broad applications. Code-based cryptosystems use error correcting codes for security and are resistant to quantum attacks. They can be applied to existing technologies to enhance encryption. The wider information security community needs to incorporate these advances in their technology. This document focuses on exploring future potential and identifying barriers and necessary research.

5 Implementation Considerations

When integrating quantum-safe cryptographic solutions into UWB or IoT-connected devices and networks, a consideration is how expensive it is to globally apply specific cryptographic primitives across all designed systems. More often than not, changes are not compatible with existing systems, making hardware and firmware updates a necessity either concurrently with standards finalization or as soon as possible after. The process of updating an entire network will involve associated logistics, lengthy timescales, and a lower-than-required adoption rate for a considerable amount of time, potentially leaving parts of the network vulnerable. Finally, it is important to point out that cryptography should adapt to the user experience, not the other way around. On a macroscopic level, this means meeting widely understood and commonly accepted network security requirements such as confidentiality and integrity. User experience in ultrawideband (UWB) with varying signal densities is complicated by resource limitations.

Quantum-safe cryptography will have different requirements in terms of key size and computational requirements, which have a direct impact on user experience. Compatibility with legacy cryptographic protocols will be essential during the transition period, and depending on any practical quantum computer asset and potential use, there may be a need to run a hybrid post-quantum security and keying protocol scheme with other parts of the network. It appears likely this will need to be part of the key exchange framework as seamless user operation is critical—whether using a local key generated by devices or for transport between devices over a network. It is very likely that there will be different implementations, with a range of key exchanges and cryptographic primitives required to suit different capabilities for different processing environments. These physical and virtual systems need to be interoperable to handle different processing environments and be secure. Compliance with relevant standards is also important to ensure the universal applicability of these new cryptographic primitives. In the case of international businesses, specific country regulations govern the way in which cryptography can be used, and this also needs to be taken into account. As broad policies generally override internal policies, a pragmatic approach is generally adopted.

5.1 Performance Considerations

The performance of a UWB or IoT system may affect the possible cryptographic solutions that can be used before the arrival of functional quantum-safe cryptographic primitives. We are planning to study performance overheads of the cryptographic solutions we may implement. This work package will look not only at the trade-off between robust security and speed of cryptographic algorithms, but also at the trade-off in different traffic types, including file transfers and live multimedia.

High levels of security in any data exchange, including heavy data exchange, will be needed to provide privacy as well as reliability of end-to-end security in a

UWB network. At the same time, an efficient level of communication must also be maintained. Historically, the security level of cryptographic algorithms in terms of key size, efficiency, etc. has passed through different eras. The post-deadline era was responsible for future security solutions. In the 1970s and 80s, data encryption techniques were rapidly being used to exchange very popular secure data. With growing computational power, complex cryptographic algorithms were also proposed, which required greater computational overhead. However, the performance of new cryptographic protocols should also be evaluated to ensure they are not significantly slower than the cryptographic methods in the system. Ongoing research in the quantum crypto-resistant field is working on equalizing this loss simultaneously with the proposed quantum security methods. Many industry standardization bodies have also made industry-relevant performance evaluations in their documents, which represent strong benchmarks suitable for these experiments.

5.2 Interoperability and Standardization

While systems for UWB and IoT services are evolving, they frequently exploit cryptographic components supporting secure communication. Consequently, the integrated operation of quantum-safe cryptographic solutions with existing implementations should be ensured. This requires extensive testing, as well as a confirmatory assessment of the compatibility between distinct cryptographic systems and devices.

With the publication of well-functioning cryptographic algorithms, solutions, and practical advice, standardization bodies aim at simplifying the conduct and widespread acceptance of secure communications. However, in the absence of available cryptographic standards and of regulatory frameworks to foster the adoption of quantum-safe cryptographic solutions, the entire cryptographic landscape of emerging quantum communications is at risk of experiencing increased fragmentation, thereby making cryptography potentially non-interoperable across the different communication segments. Fragmented security protocols impede a proper level of security. Clearly, the closer the cooperation, the greater the opportunity for mutual recognition and shared frameworks. Closeness, in turn, often requires harmonizing technical specifications and, to some extent, aligning regulatory structures. Some successful initiatives within certain narrow application areas have already been developed. In the field of financial services, a European approach to blockchain and distributed ledger technology and crypto-assets is underway. With appropriate alignment with these international initiatives, this document can assist in such efforts.

Applicability is limited by differing regulatory environments across countries. Global communications such as network-based distributed applications are predominantly covered. Popular cryptocurrencies are not within the scope of this document.

6 Results and Future direction

The fundamental works on UWB security models using the cryptographic method as used at present have different vulnerabilities. The rapid development of quantum computers tends to result in reduced secrecy for existing public-key cryptographic methods. As time goes on, the adoption of a new quantum-safe solution is mandatory. However, one can discuss longer keys to increase the security level. Post-quantum security computations are necessary but are still in the beta phase. Our belief is to integrate the ongoing research in cryptographic constructions through blockchain ledgers, SDN-enabled future networks in 5G, and Industry 4.0 IoT.

Ongoing research on large commercial algorithms is also important for security due to the scarcity of the researched algorithms. The quantum effect of industrial stakeholders is primarily increased to improve and expand the scope of quantum communication cryptography. In quantum-safe cryptography, many results require scientific collaboration and commitment from the crypto community. This paper serves as an early work on face-to-face discussions about new techniques for low-powered cryptography sharing in easy practice to secure future networks. Several research issues remain to be addressed. We are now investigating novel compact structures of the hash function for any UWB standard for Phase III IoTs. Plasma functions, enabled-privacy homomorphic algorithms, and DFV techniques are being implemented by other SDN and blockchain cryptography counterparts in collaboration with SDN and future networks. In collaboration with this, in each UWB DS and IR-UWB scheme, we propose to reduce the book size to enhance security strength in O-OFDM block scopes.

In addition, it is expected to cite one of the nanosecond iterations on the roadmap for 2026 of the UWB low and high gains. Our work also enlarges efficiency and improvement in Internet and compound techniques to secure the future of data transfer. A handful of scientists are eager to enter UWB and IoTs with software 5G works based on data transfer technology. The results of this problem are under construction and will be announced in due course. AI and cyber security cryptographic techniques are also of interest. The integrated ML real-time research prediction is part of this encryption proposal. We also invite the sector to move quantum-safe cryptography forward. We strongly encourage proposing a continuous roadmap for industrial analysts that is changing the environment with added noise signals in network OSI layers for future systems. Industry leaders in quantum-safe cryptography based on usability have been inspired to present some associates, book editors, and key companies. Future work will be available on the announcement date.

References

References

- [1] S. Shamshad, F. Riaz, R. Riaz, S. S. Rizvi et al., "An enhanced architecture to resolve public-key cryptographic issues in the internet of things (IoT), employing quantum computing supremacy," *Sensors*, 2022.
- [2] M. Hoffmann, G. Kunzmann, T. Dudda, and R. Irmer, "A secure and resilient 6G architecture vision of the German flagship project 6G-ANNA," in *IEEE*, 2023.
- [3] M. Elsanhoury, P. Mäkelä, J. Koljonen, and P. Välisuo, "Precision positioning for smart logistics using ultra-wideband technology-based indoor navigation: A review," in *IEEE*, 2022.
- [4] R. Dangi, G. Choudhary, N. Dragoni, P. Lalwani, and U. Khare, "6G Mobile Networks: Key Technologies, Directions, and Advances," **Telecom**, 2023.
- [5] O. A. Ajala, C. A. Arinze, O. C. Ofodile, and C. C. Okoye, "Exploring and reviewing the potential of quantum computing in enhancing cybersecurity encryption methods," 2024.
- [6] A. S. Al-Bayati, "Enhancing Performance of Hybrid AES, RSA and Quantum Encryption Algorithm," 2023.
- [7] S. K. Mousavi, A. Ghaffari, S. Besharat, and H. Afshari, "Security of internet of things based on cryptographic algorithms: a survey," *Wireless Networks*, 2021.
- [8] S. E. V. S. Pillai and K. Polimetla, "Analyzing the Impact of Quantum Cryptography on Network Security," in *Circuits and Communication Systems*, 2024.
- [9] G. Kirubasri, S. Sankar, D. Pandey, and B. K. Pandey, "Software-defined networking-based Ad hoc networks routing protocols," in *networking for Ad Hoc*, Springer, 2022.
- [10] M. Cheraghinia, A. Shahid, S. Luchie, "A Comprehensive Overview on UWB Radar: Applications, Standards, Signal Processing Techniques, Datasets, Radio Chips, Trends and Future Research Directions," *arXiv preprint arXiv*, 2024.
- [11] D. Coppens, A. Shahid, S. Lemey, "An overview of UWB standards and organizations (IEEE 802.15. 4, FiRa, Apple): Interoperability aspects and future research directions," *IEEE*, 2022.
- [12] A. M. Ahmed, S. A. Majeed, and Y. S. Dawood, "A Survey of 6G Mobile Systems, Enabling Technologies, and Challenges," ... & *Telecommunications*, 2023.
- [13] H. Zhang, Z. Zhang, N. Gao, Y. Xiao et al., "Cost-effective wearable indoor localization and motion analysis via the integration of UWB and IMU," *Sensors*, 2020.
- [14] W. Jiang, Z. Cao, B. Cai, and B. Li, "Indoor and outdoor seamless positioning method using UWB enhanced multi-sensor tightly-coupled integration," *IEEE Transactions on ...*, 2021.
- [15] I. Čuljak, Ž Lučev Vasić, H. Mihaldinec, and H. Džapo, "Wireless body sensor communication systems based on UWB and IBC technologies: State-of-the-art and open challenges," *Sensors*, 2020.

- [16] N. Islam, M. M. Rashid, F. Pasandideh, B. Ray, and S. Moore, "A review of applications and communication technologies for internet of things (IoT) and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) based sustainable smart farming," *Sustainability*, 2021.
- [17] M. Martalò, S. Perri, and G. Verdano, "Improved UWB TDoA-based positioning using a single hotspot for industrial IoT applications," in *IEEE Transactions*, 2021.
- [18] J. Zhang, G. Li, A. Marshall, A. Hu et al., "A new frontier for IoT security emerging from three decades of key generation relying on wireless channels," *IEEE Access*, 2020.
- [19] G. Pettorru, V. Pilloni, and M. Martalò, "Trustworthy Localization in IoT Networks: A Survey of Localization Techniques, Threats, and Mitigation," *Sensors*, 2024.
- [20] O. S. Althobaiti and M. Dohler, "Quantum-resistant cryptography for the internet of things based on location-based lattices," *IEEE Access*, 2021.
- [21] D. Chawla and P. S. Mehra, "A roadmap from classical cryptography to post-quantum resistant cryptography for 5G-enabled IoT: Challenges, opportunities and solutions," *Internet of Things*, 2023.
- [22] T. L. Scholten, C. J. Williams, D. Moody, and M. Mosca, "Assessing the benefits and risks of quantum computers," *arXiv preprint arXiv*, 2024.
- [23] J. Wang, L. Liu, S. Lyu, Z. Wang, M. Zheng, and F. Lin, "Quantum-safe cryptography: crossroads of coding theory and cryptography," **Science China**, Springer, 2022.
- [24] Kamran Ayub and Valarijs Zagurskis, "Performance Evaluation of Self Organizing Feature of Cluster-based WSN for Pilot Assisted-MAC under IR-UWB," in *Proceedings of ICMSE – 2015 International Conference on Management Science and Engineering (22nd) 2015*. IEEE Technology and Engineering Management Society. ISBN: 978-14673-65116, <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:208635650>
- [25] T. Hasija, K. R. Ramkumar, and A. Kaur, "A survey on nist selected third round candidates for post quantum cryptography," in *2022 7th International ...*, 2022.
- [26] M. E. Sabani, I. K. Savvas, D. Poulakis, and G. Garani, "Evaluation and comparison of lattice-based cryptosystems for a secure quantum computing era," *Electronics*, 2023.
- [27] Kamran Ayub , "Research on Impulse Radio's Feasibility for Wireless Sensor Network and Development of New Compatible Architecture ," PhD Thesis. Riga: RTU, 2016. 149 p, <https://ortus.rtu.lv/science/en/publications/23077>
- [28] M. M. Ali, S. J. Hashim, M. A. Chaudhary, and G. Ferré, "A Reviewing Approach to Analyze the Advancements of Error Detection and Correction Codes in Channel Coding With Emphasis on LPWAN and IoT Systems," *IEEE*, 2023. ieeexplore.ieee.org
- [29] K. Ayub and V. Zagurskis, "SMART Incubator: Implementation of Impulse Radio Ultra Wideband Based PA-MAC Architecture in Wireless Body Area Network," *2016 International Conference on Systems Informatics, Modelling and Simulation (SIMS)*, Riga, Latvia, 2016, pp. 25-31, doi: 10.1109/SIMS.2016.12.